

PRESS RELEASE

05.12.2025

Citizens' Assembly in Cologne

On **11 September 2025**, Democracy International hosted **"Democracy Unboxed: Bridging EU-German Democracy in a Comparative Analysis"** to mark the International Day of Democracy with a Citizens' Assembly in **Cologne, Germany**.

The event examined **how innovative democratic tools function both in Germany and at the EU level**, highlighting ways in which citizens can influence laws beyond elections. Bringing together experts, citizens, and civil society representatives from across Europe, the Assembly provided a space to learn, debate, and co-create ideas to strengthen democratic participation.

Participants explored the workings and implications of **two key instruments**:

- The first panel focused on German practices alongside European Citizens' Initiatives (ECIs).
- The second panel, moderated, examined the German Bürgerrat tool in comparison with European Citizens' Panels (ECPs).

Following each panel, participants engaged in hands-on workshops to **design their own initiative and assembly**. Each group developed two innovative tools, which were then presented to the wider Assembly, highlighting both the strengths and challenges of existing mechanisms. The outcomes of these discussions were collected into a set of recommendations that will be shared with the European Commission.

The Citizens' Assembly in Cologne underscored the **importance of participatory instruments** in bridging national and European democratic practices, and demonstrated how citizens can actively shape democracy beyond the ballot box.

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Citidem Project celebrated the **International Day of Democracy!**

September 15th, 2025.

The United Nations established the International Day of Democracy in 2007. Since then, more than 75 Parliaments worldwide organize annual events to celebrate it.

Democracy International, partner of the Citidem Project, organised an event on the International Day of Democracy, bringing together citizens, experts and changemakers from across Europe to explore how participatory democracy really works in Germany, at the EU level, and beyond.

Together, we explored how citizens in Germany engaged with their national democratic processes and the ways they made their voices heard. We also examined the key tools available for influencing decision-making at the EU level. Along the way, we reflected on what we could learn from each other's experiences and how these insights could be transformed into meaningful action.

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Citizen Assemblies in Ljubljana

Political Participation for All – Towards a Europe of Equals

On Thursday, 20 November 2025, as part of the CoFestival at Kino Šiška in Ljubljana, a **Citizens' Assembly** on the political participation of migrants in Slovenia "Political Participation for All – Towards a Europe of Equals" took place. The assembly **brought together more than 130 participants**, primarily migrants, refugees, asylum seekers, and representatives of organizations working in the fields of participation, inclusion, and integration (including public officials and members of international organizations). Together, we discussed issues related to participation, visibility, and representation of migrants in Slovenia. The event also aimed to develop solutions, proposals, and recommendations through collective dialogue.

Participants explored questions such as: What does participation actually mean? Are migrants, refugees, and asylum seekers truly included in society? What are we already doing within our communities? What challenges do we face daily and how can we address them together? If problems seem overwhelming, what can we still do? Do you feel seen and included in society? Do you feel a sense of belonging? And is this sometimes difficult?

Given the diverse linguistic backgrounds of participants, the assembly **was conducted in several languages and interpreted into English, Slovene, Bosnian, Arabic, and Turkish.**

In the second part of the event, participants divided into four thematic working groups:

- 1. Housing Issues** (moderator: Daniel Nzotam),
- 2. Language** (moderator: Katja Utroša),
- 3. Racism and Discrimination** (moderators: Hasan Alhallaq and Moad) and
- 4. Working Conditions and Labour Rights** (moderator: Tadej Pavkovič).

The goal of the assembly is to formulate recommendations that will be publicly presented and forwarded to relevant institutions, including the Municipality of Ljubljana, the Ministry of the Interior, the Government Office for the Support and Integration of Migrants, and the Info Point for Foreigners.

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Webinar: The Magical Idea of Citizens' Assemblies

Wednesday 3 December, 18.00-19.30 (CET)

As part of our ongoing Citizen Action for Democracy (CitiDem) series, we recently hosted a webinar titled *The Magical Idea of Citizens' Assemblies*, featuring Professor John Boswell from the University of Southampton.

During the session, Professor Boswell explored the “magic promise” of deliberative citizen engagement and examined what makes the idea of citizens' assemblies so compelling. He unpacked how this perceived magic operates from citizens' desire for meaningful participation and the sense of empowerment such processes can generate, to the way they strengthen resonance with politicians and institutions. The webinar offered valuable insights into the nuanced dynamics of citizen deliberation and provided participants with a grounded, realistic understanding of its potential and its limitations.

Citidem New Survey for young people

The Citidem project, coordinated by UNIBO, has launched a short survey to gather young people's perspectives on the current state of democracy. The survey takes approximately 10-15 minutes to complete

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